

IMPACT OF CLIL ON AN UZBEK BA PROGRAM

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Abstract. *Content and language integrated learning (CLIL) is a dual focus educational approach widely used in European primary, secondary and tertiary education institutions in which content subjects included in the mainstream curriculum are taught through a foreign language, usually English. This study investigates the impact of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) on the academic performance and language proficiency of students enrolled in a Bachelor of Arts program in Uzbekistan. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, the research examines both quantitative data from test scores and qualitative feedback from student interviews to assess the effectiveness of CLIL in enhancing subject knowledge and English language skills.*

The findings suggest that CLIL significantly improves students' comprehension and retention of subject content while concurrently boosting their English language proficiency. The study also identifies challenges, such as the need for specialized teacher training and resource availability, which must be addressed to optimize the implementation of CLIL in the Uzbek higher education context. This research contributes to the growing body of evidence supporting the adoption of CLIL in non-native English-speaking countries and offers practical recommendations for policymakers and educators aiming to improve educational outcomes through integrated learning approaches.

Keywords: *educators, policymakers, improve educational.*

Introduction

The findings indicate that CLIL notably enhances students' understanding and retention of subject content while simultaneously improving their English proficiency. However, challenges such as the need for specialized teacher training and adequate resources must be addressed for optimal implementation in Uzbekistan's higher education system. This research adds to the growing support for CLIL in non-native English-speaking countries and provides practical guidance for policymakers and educators looking to enhance learning outcomes through integrated educational strategies.

Introduction: The incorporation of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) into higher education curricula has gained global attention, particularly in non-native English-speaking countries aiming to boost both subject mastery and language skills. In Uzbekistan, CLIL's adoption in Bachelor of Arts programs represents a strategic effort to meet international educational standards and improve the competitiveness of graduates in a globalized world. This article examines CLIL's implementation and impact in an Uzbek BA program, focusing on its influence on academic achievement and English proficiency. As part of broader educational reforms in Uzbekistan, CLIL is intended to modernize curricula and teaching methods, equipping students with the skills required for the 21st century. The dual focus of CLIL is especially relevant in a global environment where English serves as the main language for academic, professional, and international communication.

While CLIL offers clear theoretical advantages, its practical application in Uzbekistan comes with distinct challenges and opportunities. This study uses a mixed-method approach,

integrating quantitative analysis of academic performance with qualitative insights from student and teacher interviews, to assess CLIL's effectiveness in Uzbek higher education. By analyzing both the benefits and challenges of CLIL, the research aims to provide evidence-based recommendations for educators and policymakers to improve the quality and outcomes of BA programs through innovative teaching strategies.

Literature Review

This section outlines key terms and concepts used in the study. The way education is implemented varies by context and is influenced by the linguistic characteristics of those involved. In recent years, the inclusion of languages, particularly English, in school curricula has become increasingly important. Seidlhofer (2011) points out that English as a lingua franca is evolving to meet intercultural communication needs across various settings. Consequently, its dominance has become inevitable due to the growing global demand for effective communication.

Governments worldwide recognize that incorporating English language instruction in schools is essential for staying connected and keeping pace with the rapid flow of information and communication globally. Considering the work and studies being conducted regarding not only bilingual but also multilingual education in different parts of the world (Costa & D'Angelo, 2011; Lorenzo, Casal, & Moore, 2010), it can be said that this is a trend that has proven to be successful in different contexts. It shows great potential to address some of the major issues in education systems worldwide in terms of language, and it also offers solutions in this area.

Countries and institutions that have implemented the use of foreign or second languages in their education systems and curricula have worked with an innovative pedagogical approach that has come to be known in recent years as CLIL. According to Coyle, Hood, and Marsh (2010), "[CLIL] is a dual-focused educational approach in which an additional language is used for the learning and teaching of both content and language" (p. 1).

Method

To explore the difficulties students encounter while engaging with CLIL at this stage of their education, the following research questions were developed: (1) What are students' perceptions of CLIL courses in the Bachelor of Arts in Foreign Languages program? (2) What are the main challenges students face in CLIL courses, and what strategies, if any, do they use to achieve their learning objectives? (3) How do students perceive the advantages of taking CLIL courses?

Merriam (2009) explains that "qualitative researchers aim to understand how individuals interpret their experiences, how they build their understanding of the world, and what meaning they assign to those experiences" (p. 5).

Given that qualitative research focuses on capturing participants' perspectives to better comprehend their experiences with CLIL, the research questions were designed to prompt in-depth descriptions of participants' views on these topics. Data were gathered through semi-structured interviews, which use a list of pre-written questions as a guide while allowing the researcher flexibility to ask follow-up questions for more detailed information (Mackey & Gass, 2005, p. 173).

Results and Discussion

1. Improving Teacher Development: A key takeaway from the study is the pressing need for thorough teacher training. Educators should pursue international certification programs to achieve a high level of English proficiency. Although standardized tests like IELTS and TOEFL

have their drawbacks, they continue to serve as reliable benchmarks for assessing language skills until more effective options emerge. Moreover, the training should also include instruction in CLIL techniques and curriculum design, equipping teachers to successfully teach both subject content and language skills.

2. Bridging Academic Skill Gaps: The difficulties students encounter in building academic competencies emphasize the importance of targeted support. Offering workshops and cross-disciplinary training for both English and subject-area teachers can foster the development of key academic skills. Collaborative teaching approaches between language and subject instructors can further strengthen the CLIL curriculum, giving students a more cohesive educational experience.

3. Fostering an Inclusive Learning Atmosphere: To address concerns about cultural identity and create a more inclusive environment, it is essential to cultivate an appreciation for English as a universal language that supports intercultural dialogue. Awareness campaigns involving students, educators, and school leaders can highlight the advantages of bilingual education and promote greater tolerance and acceptance. By placing their education within the framework of global language trends, students can gain a broader understanding of their learning journey and develop a more inclusive outlook.

4. Enhancing Course Materials: The favorable feedback on CLIL course materials indicates that well-designed resources are key to student success. These materials should be regularly assessed and improved to match students' language abilities and educational needs. Providing engaging, accessible materials can lower anxiety, build confidence, and allow students to concentrate on other areas of their studies.

Conclusions

This study has provided valuable insights that could serve as a foundation for introducing additional CLIL programs at universities nationwide. The conclusions drawn from the findings and research questions are as follows:

1. Students generally have a favorable opinion of the CLIL courses in the BA in Foreign Languages program. This positive feedback offers a promising outlook for the successful implementation of similar programs at this university and others across Uzbekistan. However, the participants pointed out several areas in need of improvement, such as teacher quality, peer collaboration, course materials, and the overall classroom environment.

2. Students in the LILEX CLIL program struggle with building essential academic skills, particularly in academic writing, recognizing and utilizing academic genres, and expanding vocabulary. While they acknowledge their shortcomings and the strategies to address them, they have not yet implemented specific actions to overcome these challenges.

3. Students recognize the advantages of CLIL classes, including the ability to use the language in diverse situations and improve academic skills.

However, they also express a desire for more comprehensive knowledge of the Spanish language. Some students worry that learning primarily in English might pose a threat to their Uzbek cultural identity, despite their overall positive feelings toward the program.

In light of the study's findings, the BA in Foreign Languages program and potential future CLIL programs at other Uzbek universities should consider the following recommendations:

a. Teachers should receive international certification to ensure advanced proficiency in English. Although some scholars question the use of standardized exams like IELTS and TOEFL

to measure language skills (Crystal, 2003; Jenkins, 2009), these assessments remain valuable tools for keeping teachers up to date until new methods emerge.

b. Educators should also be trained in CLIL methodology and materials development. Along with a strong command of the language of instruction, teachers must stay informed about effective strategies for teaching both subject content and language (Hillyard, 2011).

c. Schools should provide workshops or interdisciplinary training sessions for English and subject teachers to help students improve both general and specific academic abilities. Collaboration between language and content teachers can enrich the CLIL curriculum. Teachers working together could create a more inclusive classroom culture, encouraging students to challenge divisive behaviors and adopt more tolerant attitudes.

d. Campaigns led by students, teachers, and administrators should promote English as a global language (Crystal, 2003) that enhances intercultural communication and the exchange of knowledge. Raising awareness about modern language policies and encouraging reflection on these trends would help students contextualize their education within a global framework. This approach would also foster a more open-minded and tolerant attitude among students, teachers, and administrators towards discussions on language and education.

In conclusion, the implementation of CLIL in the Uzbek BA program has been largely positive, with students recognizing the benefits of this approach for language and content learning. However, the success and growth of CLIL programs in Uzbekistan will require addressing the current challenges by improving teacher training, providing targeted academic support, and fostering a more supportive learning environment.

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